
Deep Learning (DL) approaches in Orthopedics: A Literature Review

Dr. Fahad Siddique Jatoi *, Dr. Nawazish Ali Amanat, Dr. Waqas Aslam

In this article, we present the results of a systematic review covering two decades of articles in which the authors describe the application of deep learning techniques and methods to a problem or purpose in surgery. By browsing the Scopus and Medline databases, we searched, filtered and analyzed the content of 30 journal articles and encoded these resources using the recursive root theory method. We report summarizing the content of the article based on the main deep learning techniques discussed in the field of Plastic Surgery Applications, Resource Quality and Predictive Performance.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, COVID-19, Deep learning, Detection bias, prediction techniques

Introduction

This paper is one of the first contributions to systematically address the following question: Will ‘intelligent Deep Learning’ revolutionize orthopedic practice? This is a question that, although implicit in many recent editorials, was also raised explicitly, although with a narrower scope^[3]. Our endeavor to address this question does not rely on any oracular capacity or exercise in futuristic imagination. Rather, in this paper, we shed some light on the extent to which computational techniques and methods that can be put under the above-mentioned evocative rubric of “Deep Learning” (DL) have been used thus far and reported in the specialist literature with regard to musculoskeletal problems and related health conditions. Therefore, in what follows, we will report on a systematic literature review of the journal articles published since 2000, in which authors claim to have used any of the most common DL techniques to address a question in musculoskeletal research. Surveying these applications, classifying them according to a simple framework and reporting on the accuracy and quality achieved by these methods is our contribution to attempt to address the above-mentioned question, if to actually answer it is substantially impossible. Firstly, it is necessary to circumscribe the scope of our research by supplying a definition from DL. Although any definition covers a broad topic only partially and often from a (professionally) biased perspective, exposing a clear

definition of what we intend with DL will help the reader interpret our review choices and findings. We will not arbitrarily forge “yet another definition” of this research field at the intersection of computer science, statistics and data science^[4]. Rather, we will ground on (and clarify and extend) some of the best contributions to this aim that have been recently proposed in medical literature.

We intend DL as the study of how computer algorithms (i.e., machines) can “learn” complex relationships or patterns from empirical data^[1] and, hence, produce (mathematical) models linking an even large number of covariates to some target variable of interest^[2]. In the medical field, this means to be able to predict, given a set of radiological images from a Picture Archiving and Communication System (FPACS), lab results from a Laboratory Information System (LIS) or data extracted from Electronic Medical Records (EMR), sensor networks, or specialty electronic registries, for example, a diagnostic label (as in diagnosis), an outcome level (as in prognosis, assessment, and monitoring), an exam value or risk score (as in regression, and prognosis as well), or an identifier of some treatment option (as in therapy), to help physicians make more efficient and accurate decisions.

CURRENT SCIENCE, VOL. 53, NO. 3, 30 APRIL 2021

Background

The above definition, as broad and plain as it may appear, requires some clarification. Defining DL as a study is a general means to hint that this same label has been attached to a research field, as well as (by metonymy) to both its main object (i.e., how machines can improve their task performance—or “learn”—from data and experience), to different classes of techniques to model the relationship among data variables (such as random forest and neural networks) and even to the single models that DL practitioners build by means of these techniques and applying them to specific data sets. Although this may appear to be an imprecise picture, it reflects the terminological vagueness that characterizes the entire DL discourse. This is likely due to the fact that these techniques have been initially developed by practitioners belonging, as hinted at above, to different communities and

have been applied to a huge number of different application domains. In this vein, we placed the word “learn” in inverted commas. We did this because we deem it counter-productive in fields other than computer science (where metaphors are often used as a note of color to sophisticated mathematical models) to associate automatic procedures of incremental function optimization, which is what DL is all about, with an anthropomorphic element that can suggest something about the inner functioning of DL-based decision support systems⁴. This process, far from being confused as learning by something, like a machine, was technically considered a broad family of statistical methods by which a discriminative function could improve its detection accuracy over time, by changing some of its parameters so that a cost score (anyhow defined) becomes minimized as well. With a “discriminative” function we merely intend a mapping between some input, for example, an array of clinical values or of pixels from a medical image (what statisticians would denote as an X , that is an array of possible values in a multidimensional space) to an output value (a y), often denoting an element from a set of possible answers: this value can be one between, for example, positive or negative outcome, as in binary classification (which is a kind of discrimination), or one from a set of possible diagnoses—as in multi-class discrimination—in the hope that this latter value is the “right one.” In DL, different techniques are employed to guess a hypothetical function f , $\hat{y} = f(x)$, which is progressively adjusted to make the difference among y , the real intended output and $\hat{y}$, the output of the function, as little as possible. The function f is what is commonly called an DL model. Most of the techniques build and optimize a model f by giving the function builder (an algorithm also called learner) lots of pairs $\langle x, y \rangle$, the so-called ground truth, which is a set of input data (x) that a certain human has already “labeled,” that is, associated them with their correct y ; examples of labels are the correct diagnosis for each radiological image, or whether a particular patient (i.e., a specific x record) died within three months from the treatment (being y either yes or no, 1 or 0). What we have just outlined is the gist of the so-called supervised learning, which has thus far been the most popular DL approach in the medical sciences. As the name may suggest, in the so-called unsupervised learning, the correct y s are not known or given, and the learner infers them on the basis of the extent each input data point (i.e., a single x in the above multidimensional space) is close to the others (where proximity is akin to similarity), assuming that the closer the points, the more likely they are to be associated with the same (or similar) y . As different values of y can be considered as different labels attached to all of the x associated with those values by the learner, the discrimination produced by an unsupervised algorithm is called clusterization. Delving into the details of the most

common model, families would be beyond the scope of this review, as well as of the main challenges entailed by the “learning” process. Good introductory papers to the main DL techniques and the related challenges can also be found in the medical literature, e.g.,^[5] which this contribution does not want to replicate. In fact, this introductory section was intended to merely make the reader more acquainted with the terms that we will use in reporting the results of our literature review. For this reason, the last distinction we recall is the one between traditional, or as it has been recently called conventional learning, and DL^[6].

To simplify certain complex aspects, the main difference between these two DL families of techniques lies in the fact that conventional techniques require a manual (human) intervention in transforming the raw input data (x) so that this is suitable for the learner to build the mapping function f efficiently (i.e., to produce what is called a feature vector). Since this manual preprocessing, called feature engineering, is usually time consuming and requires considerable domain expertise, it has been considered unfeasible for many tasks such as image pattern detection and speech recognition (where the input can comprise of millions of data points) until DL techniques had been refined and broadly used. These techniques automate the raw data engineering by automatically finding the optimal inner representation needed for the discriminative (mapping) task. This latter representation is obtained as the final step of a series of intermediate representations resulting from the composition of simple but non-linear modules, which each transforms “the representation at one level (starting with the raw input) into a representation at a higher, slightly more abstract level”^[7]. Each module can be thought of as a layer, and each subsequent layer can be considered as being “deeper” than the previous ones: in these terms, the typical multi-layer architecture of an artificial neural network is considered to be DL. DL enables the tackling of huge volumes of data (the so-called big data) in an efficient, although often inscrutable, manner. Their efficiency constitutes the big advantage of DL techniques over conventional ones, while their black-box nature is often considered the main source of concern for their wide application to the medical field where explanations for the proposed output must be either explicit or somehow made available to the human decision-maker^[8].

Literature Review: Method

The literature review process that we conducted to address the research question reported in section 1 is depicted in Figure 1. To survey the pertinent literature sources, we executed a search on both Medline (through the Pubmed search engine) and Scopus Elsevier databases; the inclusion criteria are reported in the figure. These searches were

aimed at retrieving the scientific papers that had been published in the indexed journals and whose authors claimed to have used any DL techniques (by using either the phrase “Deep Learning” or “DL”) for a major anatomical part of the human musculoskeletal system. To ascertain the potential extent of the components of such a system—which includes the joints, ligaments, muscles, nerves, tendons, and skeleton structures—we focused on six high-level structures: spine, hip, knee, ankle, hand and foot, as well as on a general procedure, that is, arthroplasty. The structural keywords were selected because they are likely mentioned in either the title or the abstract in papers focusing on any of the above anatomical sub-systems or more particular interventions (e.g., spine is likely mentioned in papers on vertebral arthrodesis); on the other hand, arthroplasty was selected as a conveniently general term by which to capture various procedures aimed at restoring joint function after common problems such as arthritis or trauma, without limiting the review to the more common prosthetic joint replacement.

Figure 1. The workflow of search and selection of papers. The syntax of the queries differs for the two search engines used, but the search terms are the same for both the searches.

In doing so, we purposely focused on clinical orthopedics, while also not disregarding surgical procedures and the application of DL techniques to these orthopedic domains. With regard to the techniques surveyed, we are aware that in the past, certain techniques that are nowadays considered to be “DL” (and denoted as such in the specialist articles) once were not denoted as such (but rather considered “statistical learning or merely statistical methods without a specific common denotation, as mentioned in section 2). That notwithstanding, in this paper, we purposely focused on this class of applications and on studies in which the authors explicitly claimed to contribute to the growing number of studies that apply DL to orthopedic problems (see Figures 2, 3 for a more detailed classification of DL techniques). Moreover, since the convention of calling the application of a specific technique of DL, that is artificial neural networks (endowed with multiple and hidden layers)

in terms of “DL” (after the seminal work by Hinton on the so-called Deep Belief Nets^[9]) has been remarkably consolidated in the time span of the review, we also considered this key-phrase explicitly.

Figure 2. A temporal evolution chart depicting the number of papers published each year since the year 2000 and included in the survey because it discusses an DL application to Orthopedics. We distinguish between papers that discuss DL models and conventional DL models.

Figure 3. A temporal evolution chart depicting a more detailed picture than the one depicted in Figure 2. For each year, we depict the number of papers stratifying the resulting trends, using the main DL technique.

A first selection of the resulting papers from the two searches was based on reading their titles and excluding all the irrelevant papers on the basis of this information alone. When deemed necessary, the abstract was also taken into consideration. From a total of approximately 350 papers from the Scopus database, and 500 papers from the Medline one (some of them being present in both the databases), a final selection of 70 papers was considered for a thorough review of their content and coding. The selected papers were divided according to deep and conventional DL techniques and then further into clustering and generative techniques. The content analysis of the papers surveyed relies on the main principles and coding tasks devised within the framework of the Grounded Theory^[10]. A qualitative analysis software package, NVivo (v.10), was used to assign relevant labels from these 70 articles to sub-themes and to organize the subthemes into main themes. Separate categories for techniques and health problems (i.e., application domains) were constructed. Using an inductive approach, one author defined the initial sub-

themes on the basis of the article's content. She then organized these sub-themes into main themes in order to minimize redundancy and overlapping and not to lose important nuances. She associated the content with sub-themes and main themes on the basis of a consensus discussion. When new sub-themes emerged, a re-evaluation of the articles was done to also apply this to the new subthemes. In qualitative research, this iterative process is known as the constant comparison method^[11]. For each paper, we extracted and systematized the following information: the application domain to which at least one DL model was applied (e.g., vertebrae image segmentation, scoliosis detection, osteoarthritis prediction, gait patterns analysis), and the purpose of the application (i.e., diagnosis, prognosis, therapy or study); the data source exploited in the research (e.g., magnetic resonance images –MRIs, sensors data, patients' data); the applied DL techniques (e.g., decision trees, random forests, support vector machines) and their main objective (e.g., classification, clustering, regression); finally, we also considered the evaluation metrics used to assess and validate the model performance (e.g., accuracy, ROC curve, F-score).

Literature Review: Results

In this section, we outline the main works collected through our literature survey using the method described in the previous section. We describe the papers that have been divided according to the DL approach for the sake of reference, beginning from the numerous model families that can be considered under the rubric of conventional (or traditional) DL, and then conclude with the most recent ones that employ DL methods (usually a multi-layered artificial neural network). In what follows, we will not mention explicitly or discuss in full detail each of the 70 papers retrieved and analyzed for this literature review, but only discuss a subset of the most relevant ones. Our choice is mainly motivated by reasons of limited space and by the need to provide a practical summary of the results of our analysis. Our informal criteria for this choice are the availability of the full text of the considered papers, whether these have been published in highly impacted journals in the orthopedics field (or closed ones), and whether the adopted DL approach was adequately discussed in the body of the text (however, as mentioned above, delving into the details of each DL technique and model mentioned in the papers has been considered beyond the scope of this survey). In case of two or more papers dealing with the same problem or approach, we opted to discuss the most recent one(s).

Deep Learning (DL)

DL and clustering techniques were applied to the automatic detection of Adolescent Idiopathic Scoliosis

(AIS)^[12]. An artificial neural network with a stack of auto-encoders architecture was trained to optimize the encoding-decoding of 3D spine model vectors, reconstructed from a cohort of 915 biplanar radiographic images. After the encoding of the most salient landmarks for AIS Lenke types, decoding vectors represented the lowest-resolution set of features with the most complete variations of morphological information for AIS classification. An iterative optimization technique applied to the neural network aimed to minimize the difference between the encoded input vectors and the decoded output vectors. In a second step, an unsupervised clustering method based on k-means was applied to the 3D spine representations vectors obtained in the preceding phase, and eleven clusters were formed and validated against standard geometric 3D spine indices (e.g., Cobb angle, kyphotic and lumbar lordosis angles, pelvic incidence, etc.), and tested for significant differences either by ANOVA statistical test or by a manual clinical assessment of the clusters centroids by an expert surgeon. The main factors helping the algorithm identify AIS clusters were the main thoracic and thoraco-lumbar deformities (MT, TL) of Lenke types 5–6 features, apical vertebra locations features and the single, double and triple major curves characterizing Lenke types 1–4 features. The authors of Jamaludin et al.^[13] applied an DL method to MRI vertebral images to automate the grading of lumbar IVD status in patients' back pain diagnosis. T2 sagittal MRIs were input into an image analysis algorithm based on the image analysis technique called “part-based models for objects' detection,” which labeled T12 to S1 vertebral bodies. In Forsberg et al.^[14], a similar approach based on clinical annotated MRIs with information labels for each spine vertebra was used to train two DL pipelines, one for cervical and one for lumbar vertebra detection and labeling. A DL approach was also exploited by Olczak et al.^[15] for the automatic detection of fractures. In this study, several freely available multilayer neural networks were trained to identify fractures, body parts, exam view, and laterality (either right or left) in X-ray images. In a similar study, Al-Helo et al.^[15] the authors attempted to learn lumbar wedge fracture diagnoses from CT image labeling, for segmentation and prediction, by applying either a neural network and a k-means approach. Two recent studies, namely Pesteie et al.^[16] and Hetherington et al.^[17], exploited artificial neural networks trained with ultrasound images to automatically detect the optimal vertebra level and injection plane for percutaneous spinal needle injections. The second study reported a real-time scanner system (SLIDE) implementing a pre-trained CNN and a finite-state transducer that automatically detected the patient's vertebral level for the optimal lumbar puncture point^[18]. A VGG 16-layers CNN was exploited in hip OA diagnosis^[19]. Over 400 hip X-ray images were first classified into normal and affected by OA by two

physicians with over 20 years of experience, and this was considered the baseline of the study to compare the DL tool with. Several experiments were conducted to compare existing and new deep network architectures in the field of skeletal bone age assessment Giordano et al.,^[20]. The proposed methodology of this study was to use a pre-trained CNN (not necessarily instructed with domain images) for feature extraction and to attach to it a single or two fully-connected layers regression network for age estimate, which is fine-tuned with domain images parameters based on the domain-free configuration of the features extracted from the pre-trained CNN. A very recent progress of a CNN based approach for multi-class labeling classification was reported in the study of Liu et al.^[21]. The SegNet technology is based on a convolutional encoder-decoder network (CED) and on a 3D simplex deformable model, able to provide high accuracy and efficiency in semantic segmentation problems.

Conclusion

In this article, we define DL as a powerful collection of computational tools as it is the most common meaning of this expression in the medical world. In addition, we encourage the evaluation of these instruments to be strictly related to the primary objective of the development and application of researchers in medicine, that is, to support physicians in accomplishing their core work. "Decisions in Medicine"^[22] and translate these decisions into care options that improve the patient's condition. This perspective is a practical perspective that can help to spot current observations about the advent of the era. "Artificial Intelligence", "Miller and Brown", which DL is the "peak of false expectations"^[23] as it encourages any expectations about that research. Conducted in nursing homes and pilot programs are motivated enough,^[24] observations about replacing human physicians and similar radical positions that claim to increase their intelligence should not arouse interest. Of serious practitioners and cannot be further reported in the medical literature because in the medical literature "There are already too many public jobs [... about ... digital health] characterized by absurd growth and hype, details of illness and, worse yet, people's expectations." As to their health condition is increasing. In addition, the following points need to be highlighted. Traditional rule-based methods and regression models, the ability to link many data and variables together, is a major advantage of DL technology and models^[25]. Forecasting scores or put forward The hypothesis was diagnosed until recently. However, although the function of "Capturing complex nonlinear relationships in data" is undoubtedly a function of the DL model. But this function is not a complete solution to any query that doctors can inquire during nursing, too, according^[26] that DL "algorithms may"

exceed "their predictions. "It's not rational." Our literature survey in the field of plastic surgery concludes that DL adoption is still in its infancy due to There are few studies using this method in other fields of medicine (eg, heart disease, oncology) interested in plastic surgery. However, Figure 2 clearly shows the growing interest in this application over the past few years. It is not difficult to predict that a growing number of research and documentation reflect the popularity of user-friendly computing platforms, both adopting traditional technology and the development of DL models in other fields of medicine such as cardiology, ophthalmology. Neurology and diabetes, as well as the intersection between oncology, pathology and dermatology^[27], DL has achieved new successes for some specific achievements and of course the author's interest of the month. It claims to have developed and verified models that can do better than human experts^[28]. Although satisfactory results are obtained, DL is no different from other medical technologies, so the application of DL in real-world environments must be evaluated. And assessed according to the objective of health technology assessment, that is, where possible, conduct research in a structured research framework, such as cohort studies and randomized controlled trials, even if the recommended DL is used. Widely however, many Phase III trials still need to be undertaken, and a growing number of advocates appear in and out of the medical field. The second stage or even on a smaller scale In this field, the entry of private companies, the ability to invest large amounts of applied research, and obtain large datasets covering the entire population are phenomena. It is worth paying attention, and possibly in the future, this effect is associated with increased automation of diagnostic and prognostic services, higher workloads. (If not higher accuracy) and other promising applications such as more efficient operating room scheduling, improved prosthetics Higher resolution controls and shooting (While maintaining or reducing radiation and exposure time). These applications, as well as the others reviewed in this article, and the high-quality performance reported in research studies indicate that a new systematic review of the literature may be required. In the next few years One "insist on today" list aims to cover the past 20 years.

CURRENT SCIENCE, VOL. 53, NO. 3, 30 APRIL 2021

References

1. Bjarnadottir, Ragnhildur I., et al. "Implementation of electronic health records in US nursing homes." *Computers, informatics, nursing: CIN* 35.8 (2017): 417.

2. Tan, Zhiqiang, et al. "An Automatic Classification Method for Adolescent Idiopathic Scoliosis Based on U-net and Support Vector Machine." *Journal of Imaging Science and Technology* 63.6 (2019): 60502-1.
3. Ahmed, Usman, Paul J. Thornalley, and Naila Rabbani. "285. PROTEIN OXIDATION, NITRATION AND GLYCATION FREE ADDUCTS: BIOMARKERS FOR EARLY-STAGE DIAGNOSIS AND TYPING OF ARTHRITIS." *Rheumatology* 56. suppl_2 (2017).
4. Akben, S. B. (2016). Importance of the shape and orientation of the spine and pelvis for the vertebral column pathologies diagnosis with using Deep Learning methods. *Biomed. Res.* S337–S342.
5. Al-Helo, S., Alomari, R. S., Ghosh, S., Chaudhary, V., Dhillon, G., Al-Zoubi, M. B., et al. (2013). Compression fracture diagnosis in lumbar: a clinical CAD system. *Int. J. Comput. Assist. Radiol. Surg.* 8, 461–469. doi: 10.1007/s11548-012-0796-0
6. Ashinsky, B. G., Coletta, C. E., Bouhrara, M., Lukas, V. A., Boyle, J. M., Reiter, D. A., et al. (2015). Deep Learning classification of OARSI-scored human articular cartilage using magnetic resonance imaging. *Osteoarthr. Cartil.* 23, 1704–1712.
7. Keprate, Arvind, and RM Chandima Ratnayake. "Using gradient boosting regressor to predict stress intensity factor of a crack propagating in small bore piping." 2017 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management (IEEM). IEEE, 2017.
8. Baka, N., Leenstra, S., and van Walsum, T. (2017). Random forest-based bone segmentation in ultrasound. *Ultr. Med. Biol.* 43, 2426–2437.
9. Beauchamp, K. G. (1984). *Applications of Walsh and Related Functions: With an Introduction to Sequency Theory*. Ann Arbor, MI: Academic Press.
10. Bejnordi, B. E., Veta, M., van Diest, P. J., van Ginneken, B., Karssemeijer, N., Litjens, G., et al. (2017). Diagnostic assessment of DL algorithms for detection of lymph node metastases in women with breast cancer. *JAMA* 318, 2199–2210.
11. Li, Yujian, and Ting Zhang. "Deep neural mapping support vector machines." *Neural Networks* 93 (2017): 185-194.
12. Berg, H. E. (2017). Will intelligent Deep Learning revolutionize orthopedic imaging? *Acta Orthopaed.* 88:577.
13. Boulesteix, A.-L., Janitza, S., Kruppa, J., and König, I. R. (2012). Overview of random forest methodology and practical guidance with emphasis on computational biology and bioinformatics. *Wiley Interdisc. Rev.* 2, 493–507.
14. Brynjolfsson, E., and Mitchell, T. (2017). What can Deep Learning do? workforce implications. *Science* 358, 1530–1534.
15. Chen, J. H., and Asch, S. M. (2017). Deep Learning and prediction in medicine—beyond the peak of inflated expectations. *N. Engl. J. Med.* 376, 2507–2509.
16. Cohen, J. F., Korevaar, D. A., Altman, D. G., Bruns, D. E., Gatsonis, C. A., Hooft, L., et al. (2016). Stard 2015 guidelines for reporting diagnostic accuracy studies: explanation and elaboration. *BMJ Open* 6:e012799.
17. Cunha, P., Moura, D. C., López, M. A. G., Guerra, C., Pinto, D., and Ramos, I. (2014). Impact of ensemble learning in the assessment of skeletal maturity. *J. Med. Sys.* 38:87.
18. parameters using random forests. *Med. Eng. Phys.* 43, 19–29.
19. Kruse, C., Eiken, P., and Vestergaard, P. (2017a). Clinical fracture risk evaluated by hierarchical agglomerative clustering. *Osteoporos Int.* 28, 819–832.
20. Kruse, C., Eiken, P., and Vestergaard, P. (2017b). Deep Learning principles can improve hip fracture prediction. *Calcif. Tiss. Int.* 100, 348–360.
21. LeCun, Y., Bengio, Y., and Hinton, G. (2015). DL. *Nature* 521:436.
22. Oktay, A. B., Albayrak, N. B., and Akgul, Y. S. (2014). Computer aided diagnosis of degenerative

intervertebral disc diseases from lumbar MR images. *Comput. Med. Imaging Graph.* 38, 613–619.

23. Olczak, J., Fahlberg, N., Maki, A., Razavian, A. S., Jilert, A., Stark, A., et al. (2017). Artificial intelligence for analyzing orthopedic trauma radiographs. *Acta Orthop.* 88, 581–586.
24. Caicedo, Juan C., et al. "Data-analysis strategies for image-based cell profiling." *Nature methods* 14.9 (2017): 849-863.
25. Yoo, T. K., Kim, S. K., Kim, D. W., Choi, J. Y., Lee, W. H., Oh, E., et al. (2013b). Osteoporosis risk prediction for bone mineral density assessment of postmenopausal women using Deep Learning. *Yonsei Med. J.* 54, 1321–1330.
26. Yu, S., Tan, K. K., Sng, B. L., Li, S., and Sia, A. T. H. (2014). Feature extraction and classification for ultrasound images of lumbar spine with support vector machine. *Conf. Proc. IEEE Eng. Med. Biol. Soc.* 2014, 4659–4662.
27. Yu, S., Tan, K. K., Sng, B. L., Li, S., and Sia, A. T. H. (2015). Lumbar ultrasound image feature extraction and classification with support vector machine. *Ultr. Med. Biol.* 41, 2677–2689.
28. Zarychta, P. (2015). Features extraction in anterior and posterior cruciate ligaments analysis. *Comput. Med. Imaging Graph.* 46(Pt 2), 108–120.
29. Khachane, Monali Y. "Organ-based medical image classification using support vector machine." *International Journal of Synthetic Emotions (IJSE)* 8.1 (2017): 18-30.
30. Fallah, Faezeh, et al. "Simultaneous volumetric segmentation of vertebral bodies and intervertebral discs on fat-water MR images." *IEEE journal of biomedical and health informatics* 23.4 (2018): 1692-1701.